

Dyes derived from Imidazole-dicarboxylic Acid.

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The present communication is the second* of the series of researches that have been undertaken by the present authors in order to establish that the effect of a doubly linked nitrogen atom in a ring system contained in a dye molecule is not to lighten the colour as found by Ghosh (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 118, 1102), but on the contrary to intensify it in most instances. Quantitative measurements of absorption spectra of the various dyes containing doubly linked nitrogen in the ring which are being prepared in this laboratory, and which will be published collectively along with the last paper of the series, tend to show that the effect of a doubly linked nitrogen atom in the ring is to intensify the colour to a certain extent as compared with the corresponding substances containing carbon in place of nitrogen.

With the above object in view, imidazole-dicarboxylic acid has been condensed with various aromatic amino and hydroxy-compounds, and the corresponding dyestuffs obtained. The condensations, as a rule, take place without the use of any condensing agents, but it has been found more suitable to use small quantities of strong sulphuric acid, or tin tetrachloride in most of the cases in order to get better yields of the products. The following substances have been made to condense with imidazole-dicarboxylic acid and the corresponding dyestuffs obtained: phenol, resorcinol, catechol, phloroglucinol, hydroxy-quinol, and *m*-phenylenediamine. In general properties these substances are quite similar to the corresponding phthaleins, but the intensity of colour is slightly greater, and in this respect they are more in accordance with the corresponding quinolineins (Ghosh, *loc. cit.*).

EXPERIMENTAL.

Phenol-imidazolein.

* The first of these papers was published in this *Journal*, 1926, 3, 161.

A mixture of imidazole-dicarboxylic acid (one mol.), phenol (two mols. plus 20 per cent. excess) and tin tetrachloride (one mol. plus 20 per cent. excess) was heated at 100-110° for about 18 hours. The melt was then poured into water and the excess of phenol distilled off in steam. The residue, after filtration, was extracted with dilute ammonium hydroxide, and the filtered ammoniacal extract acidified with hydrochloric acid. The precipitated crystalline mass was collected and recrystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless needles, melting at 282°. It dissolves in alkalis with a bright pink colour. (Found : N, 9.49. $C_{11}H_{11}O_4N_2$ requires N, 9.09 per cent.).

Resorcinol-imidazomalein.

A mixture of imidazole-dicarboxylic acid (one mol.), resorcinol (two mols.) and a few drops of concentrated sulphuric acid was heated at 150-160° for about three hours. The melt was then extracted with dilute sodium hydroxide and the filtered extract precipitated with hydrochloric acid. The precipitated dyestuff was then crystallised from a large volume of hot water in yellow needles. When heated the substance blackens at 280-285° and melts with decomposition at 267°. It dissolves in alkalis with an orange-red colour and a fine green fluorescence. (Found : N, 9.02. $C_{17}H_{16}O_4N_2$ requires N, 8.69 per cent.).

Phloroglucinol-imidazomalein.

The condensation with phloroglucinol was effected exactly as in the above instance with the difference that the temperature was kept at 200° for about 4 hours. The isolation and purification of the dyestuff were also done in the same manner. The substance crystallises in orange-yellow needles and dissolves in alkalis with

a blood-red colour but without any fluorescence ; m.p. above 260°. (Found: N, 8.2. C₁₇H₁₀O₇N₂ requires N, 7.91 per cent.).

Hydroxyquinol-imidasomalestin.

The condensation with hydroxyquinol was effected exactly as in the above two instances with the difference that the temperature was kept at 130-140° for about two hours. The melt was extracted with alcohol and the alcoholic extract, after filtration, cautiously diluted with water, which caused the precipitation of the dyestuff in the form of brownish flocks. It could not be crystallised. It dissolves in alkalis with a bright pink colour and melts with decomposition at 258-260°. (Found: N, 8.1. C₁₇H₁₀O₇N₂ requires N, 7.91 per cent.).

Catechol-imidasomalestin.

The condensation with catechol was effected exactly as in the case with phenol. The melt was then thoroughly ground and washed with water acidified with hydrochloric acid. The residue was then extracted with alcohol and the alcoholic extract, after filtration, cautiously diluted with water which caused the precipitation of the dyestuff. It could not be crystallised. It dissolves in alkalis with a transient green colour. (Found: N, 8.82. C₁₇H₁₀O₇N₂ requires N, 8.69 per cent.).

m-Phenylenediamine-imidasomalestin.

A mixture of imidazole-dicarboxylic acid (one mol.) and m-phenylenediamine hydrochloride (two mols. plus 10 per cent. excess) was cautiously heated in a test tube in the naked flame until the melt assumed a dark red colour. The melt was then allowed to cool and then finely powdered. It was then extracted with absolute alcohol and the alcoholic extract very carefully diluted

with water which slowly deposited the dyestuff in fine brownish yellow needles. The substance dissolves in alcohol with a bright yellow colour and a green fluorescence. In dilute acids the colour of the solution is red without any fluorescence; m.p. above 290°. (Found: N, 22.31. $C_{17}H_{13}O_2N$, requires N, 21.94 per cent.).

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